

COSA NOSTRA TERROR GROUP: ORIGINS, HISTORY AND STRUCTURE

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ORIGINS

THE ROMAN EMPIRE, IT IS ESTIMATED, WAS ESTABLISHED IN THE FIRST CENTURY BCE BY JULIUS CAESAR, FOLLOWING MANY CENTURIES OF ROMAN REPUBLIC EXPANSION. ALTHOUGH THE REPUBLIC WOULD CONTINUE IN NAME, THE EMPEROR THEN HAD ALL MEANINGFUL AUTHORITY. THE EMPIRE, WHICH REACHED ITS HEIGHT IN 117 CE, WOULD LATER BE DIVIDED IN TWO: A WESTERN PART, WHICH WOULD BE INVADDED AND CONQUERED IN 476 CE BY ODOACER'S ARMY, AND THE MORE SUCCESSFUL EASTERN PART, WITH ITS CAPITAL IN BYZANTIUM (RENAMED 'CONSTANTINOPLE'), WHICH WOULD CARRY ON UNTIL SULTAN MEHMET 2 CONQUERED WHAT WAS LEFT OF IT IN 1453 CE.

AFTER 476 CE, WHAT WAS LEFT OF THE ROMAN ARISTOCRACY REGROUPED AND WERE ASSISTED BY THE EASTERN ROMAN (BYZANTINE) EMPIRE TO RETAKE ROME AND ITALY. DESPITE SOME INITIAL SUCCESSES, MOST OF EUROPE WAS EVENTUALLY OVERRUN BY THE FRANKS, LOMBARDS, GOTHs AND OTHER TRIBES. FRANCIA EMERGED AS THE DOMINANT KINGDOM, RULED BY THE MEROVINGIAN DYNASTY.

HOWEVER, ASSISTED BY THEIR INVESTMENTS AND CONNECTIONS IN THE BYZANTINE EMPIRE, THEY WERE ABLE TO FINANCE A CLANDESTINE CAMPAIGN TO REGAIN CONTROL OF THEIR LOST EMPIRE. ROMAN INTELLIGENCE, JUST LIKE EARLIER INCARNATIONS SUCH AS THE FRUMENTARIi, WERE A ROMAN MILITARY ORGANISATION, SIMILAR IN MANY WAYS TO A MODERN DAY INTELLIGENCE AGENCY. THEY'D BEGUN THEIR HISTORY AS A COURIER SERVICE AND DEVELOPED INTO AN IMPERIAL SPYING AGENCY. THEIR ORGANISATION WOULD ALSO CARRY OUT ASSASSINATIONS. AFTER THE ROMAN DEFEAT, THEY STILL HAD A CONSIDERABLE SPY NETWORK ALL OVER THE EX-WESTERN ROMAN EMPIRE, INCLUDING MANY SPIES IN ROMAN-BUILT CITIES, SUCH AS MERCHANTS, CRAFTSMEN, SCRIBES, SCHOLARS, EX-SOLDIERS AND OTHERS OF ROMAN DESCENT. THEY MIGHT HAVE ALSO HAVE BEEN KNOWN BY THE NAME, 'THE BLACK HAND', A REFERENCE TO A ROTTEN HAND CUT FROM A CORPSE OR LIVE PERSON, TO BE USED AS A CEREMONIAL ITEM IN A RELIGIOUS, PROBABLY PAGAN OR WITCHCRAFT, CEREMONY.

IN SPITE OF THEIR MILITARY WEAKNESS, THEY HAD SUFFICIENT FUNDS TO BUILD UP SEVERAL ITALIAN CITIES, AND TWO IN PARTICULAR, VENICE (FROM THE 6TH CENTURY CE ONWARDS), AND LATER GENOA, TO TRADE WITH THE BYZANTINE EMPIRE, AND GENERATE FUNDING NEEDED FOR THEIR OPERATIONS. SAILING TO AND FROM THE BYZANTINE EMPIRE ALSO ASSISTED THEM TO RECEIVE FUNDING, INTELLIGENCE AND DIRECTION FROM BYZANTINE EMPIRE INTELLIGENCE.

THEY EMPLOYED STANDARD FOREIGN INTELLIGENCE TACTICS SUCH AS SUBVERSION, SEDITION, ESPIONAGE, SABOTAGE, RECONNAISSANCE AND ASSASSINATION, TO UNDERMINE AND REPLACE THE FRANKISH ARISTOCRACY. THEY WOULD THEN BUILD UP THE POPULATION OF EUROPE AND THEIR TECHNOLOGICAL ADVANTAGE FOR A MILITARY CAMPAIGN TO TAKE OVER THE ENTIRE WORLD.

THEY ESTABLISHED FRONT ORGANISATIONS TO RAISE MONEY, EMPLOYING PSYCHOLOGICAL MANIPULATION AND BUSINESS ACUMEN TO GAIN INFLUENCE, GATHER INTELLIGENCE, RECRUIT PEOPLE, AND GENERATE FUNDING FOR THEIR CAUSE.

THEIR FIRST OBJECTIVE WOULD BE TO RECRUIT MEMBERS OF THE EUROPEAN NOBILITY AND

MEMBERS OF ROYAL HOUSEHOLDS. THEY WOULD THEN ATTEMPT TO INFILTRATE THE EUROPEAN NOBILITY THROUGH INTERMARRIAGE, WITH A VIEW TO TAKING OVER KINGDOMS. THE BLACK NOBILITY WOULD AIM TO REPLACE THE ENTIRE FRANKISH, GOTHIC AND LORBARD NOBILITY WITH THEIR DESCENDANTS, AND BUILD UP THE POPULATION OF EUROPE TO INVADE OTHER PARTS OF THE WORLD IN ORDER TO ESTABLISH A WORLD EMPIRE. THEY WOULD THEN ELIMINATE ALL OPPOSITION, AND THEN FINALLY CALL THEIR EMPIRE, NOW WORLD-WIDE, THE ROMAN EMPIRE, IMPERIUM ROMANUM.

IT IS THOUGHT THEY CALLED THEIR CAUSE 'RES NOSTRA', WHICH MEANS 'OUR THING', OR 'OUR MATTER', OR IN ITALIAN, 'COSA NOSTRA'. BUT IN FACT, THEY MIGHT HAVE CALLED THEIR CLANDESTINE ORGANISATION, 'CAUSAE NOSTRAE', WHICH IN ENGLISH IS TRANSLATED AS 'OUR CAUSE', OR IN ITALIAN, AS 'CAUSA NOSTRA'.

A BRIEF HISTORY OF KEY EVENTS, 476 CE - PRESENT (2023 CE):

476 CE: ROME FALLS. CAUSA NOSTRA (CN) SECRET SOCIETY ESTABLISHED TO RE-ESTABLISH THE WESTERN ROMAN EMPIRE, IMPERIUM ROMANUM (IR), AND TAKE OVER THE WORLD.

675 - 751 CE: THE CN TAKES OVER THE FRANKISH MONARCHY AFTER THE MEROVINGIAN DYNASTY IS REPLACED BY THEIR TREACHEROUS MAYORS OF THE PALACE (HEADS OF THEIR ROYAL HOUSEHOLD), THE CAROLINGIANS (CN AGENTS), AFTER THE MURDER OF CHILDERIC 2 AND DAGOBERT 2 BY CN ASSASSINS.

756 CE: STEPHEN 2 (A ROMAN ARISTOCRAT AND MEMBER OF THE ORSINI FAMILY, A CN FAMILY THOUGHT TO DESCEND FROM THE ROMAN MAXIMUS FAMILY), DUKE OF ROME, RECEIVES TERRITORIES FROM PEPIN THE SHORT (CN) WHICH HAD BELONGED TO THE ROMAN EMPIRE, RESTABLISHING A SMALL ROMAN STATE.

774 CE: THE CN TAKE OVER THE KINGDOM OF THE LOMBARDS. THE LOMBARD MONARCHS ARE REPLACED BY THE CAROLINGIANS (CN) AFTER CHARLES 1 OF FRANCE (CN) CONQUERED THE LOMBARDS AT THE INVITATION OF ADRIAN 1 OF ROME (CN).

800 CE: CHARLES 1 OF FRANCE (CN) IS CROWNED AS ROMAN EMPEROR, MAKING REESTABLISHMENT OF THE ROMAN EMPIRE OFFICIAL, THOUGH WITH A VENEER OF FRANKISH OVERLORDSHIP.

950 CE: CONSEQUENT TO THE REVIVAL OF LIFE AND TRADE WITHIN THE OLD ROMAN WALLS OF THE CITY OF LONDON (FORMERLY THE ROMAN EMPIRE COLONY LONDINIUM) BY ALFRED THE GREAT IN 886 CE, A DRAMATIC INCREASE IN TRADE, WITH ITS ROMAN, PARTICULARLY MERCHANT, POPULATION, OCCURS, ENRICHING THE CITY.

1066 CE: THE SAXON MONARCHY OF ENGLAND (ELECTED THROUGH THE WYTAN) IS REPLACED BY THAT OF WILLIAM THE BASTARD (CN), AFTER CONSPIRING WITH HARALD 3 OF NORWAY (CN), ALEXANDER 2 OF ROME (CN), AND PROBABLY CN BURGHERS OF THE CITY OF LONDON, TO INVADE AND OVERTHROW HAROLD 2 OF ENGLAND. WILLIAM WAS DUE TO ATTACK SOUTHERN ENGLAND AS HARALD 3 ATTACKED THE NORTH, TO DIVIDE HAROLD 2'S FORCES. THEY WOULD THEN DIVIDE ENGLAND BETWEEN THEM. WILLIAM, HOWEVER, BETRAYED HARALD 3 AND WAITED FOR HIM TO ATTACK FIRST, SO THAT HAROLD 2 SUFFERED MAXIMUM DAMAGE TO HIS ARMY, AND HAD TO MARCH NORTH, THEN BACK SOUTH, TO FACE WILLIAM WITH A MUCH DEPLETED, FATIGUED FORCE. HARALD 3 WAS KILLED IN THE FIGHTING AT STAMFORD BRIDGE. WILLIAM TOOK OVER ENGLAND. THOUGH THE BAYEUX TAPESTRY TELLS A TALE OF HAROLD 2 BEING KILLED IN BATTLE WITH AN ARROW THROUGH THE EYE, THERE IS LITTLE EVIDENCE HE DIED AT HASTINGS. WILLIAM, NOW WILLIAM 1 OF ENGLAND, IS PREVENTED FROM TAKING CONTROL OF LONDON BY ALEXANDER 2. HE GRANTS

THE CITY OF LONDON A CHARTER IN 1075, LEGALLY ACKNOWLEDGING THEIR INDEPENDENCE, FOR WHICH REASON THE CITY IS NOT INCLUDED IN THE DOMESDAY BOOK OF 1086 CE, AS IT IS NOT A PART OF ENGLAND, AND IS THUS BEYOND ROYAL CONTROL.

1075 CE: A PROTRACTED CONFLICT BEGINS BETWEEN THE ALLIES OF THE HOUSE OF HOHENSTAUFEN (GHIBELLINES) AND THE ALLIES OF THE HOUSE OF WELF (GUELPHS), CN, FOR SUPREMACY IN EUROPE THROUGH CONTROL OF THE PAPACY AND THE ('HOLY') ROMAN EMPIRE. THE CONFLICT INCLUDES THE INVESTITURE CONTROVERSY, RESOLVED BY THE CONCORDAT OF WORMS IN 1122 CE. GUELPH FAMILIES LIKE THE ORSINI AND ESTE FAMILIES, AND GHIBELLINE FAMILIES LIKE THE COLONNA, CARRY ON THE STRUGGLE UNTIL 1559 CE.

1113 CE: PASCHAL 2 OF ROME CONFIRMS THE EXISTENCE OF THE ORDER OF KNIGHTS OF THE HOSPITAL OF SAINT JOHN OF JERUSALEM, KNOWN AS KNIGHTS ST JOHN OR KNIGHTS HOSPITALLER, A CN FRONT ORGANISATION OPEN ONLY TO THE NOBILITY. IT SEEMS TO HAVE BEGUN OPERATIONS AROUND 1099, INFLUENCED IN ITS EARLY DEVELOPMENT BY MERCHANTS FROM AMALFI AND SALERNO, ON THE AMALFITAN COAST. THAT REGION OF ITALY WAS STILL HELD BY THE BYZANTINE EMPIRE UP UNTIL 661 CE, THEN IT BECAME A BYZANTINE SATELLITE STATE, THE DUCHY OF NAPLES, STILL LATER, THE DUCHY OF

AMALFI FROM 958 UNTIL 1136 CE, WHEREUPON IT BECAME A PART OF THE KINGDOM OF SICILY. THE BYZANTINE EMPIRE WAS ALLIED WITH THE NORMANS WHO WOULD RULE SICILY, AND THERE WAS A SUBSTANTIAL BYZANTINE SPY NETWORK IN THE REGION, MAKING IT A CN STRONGHOLD. ST JOHN OF JERUSALEM WAS CHOSEN AS THE PATRON SAINT OF THE ORDER AS THE EAGLE IS HIS SYMBOL. THE ROMAN EAGLE WAS THE STANDARD OF A ROMAN LEGION, AND CAME TO SYMBOLISE THE ROMAN MILITARY, IMPERIAL RULE AND AUTHORITY, AND THE ROMAN EMPIRE GENERALLY. THUS, IT WAS, AND IS, AN IMPORTANT CN SYMBOL. DIFFERING FROM THE EQUESTRIAN ORDER OF ANCIENT ROME, THE KNIGHTS ARE A COVERTLY ROMAN MILITARY ORGANISATION, AND BECAUSE THEY ENJOY MANY PRIVILEGES, SUCH AS EXEMPTION FROM LOCAL ALLEGIANCE AND LAW, EXCEPT ROMAN LAW, THEY PROVE EFFECTIVE AS A RECRUITING AND FUNDRAISING ARM FOR THE CN, WITH MANY OF THE EUROPEAN NOBILITY JOINING AND DONATING TO THE ORDER. THEY EXPERIENCE RAPID GROWTH AND THE MODEL WILL BE REPLICATED IN SUCH FURTHER ORDERS AS THE KNIGHTS TEMPLAR, THE TEUTONIC KNIGHTS, THE KNIGHTS OF ST JAMES AND THE KNIGHTS OF SAINT LAZARUS. THEY PRACTICE MEDICINE AS A COVER FOR THEIR ACTIVITIES, FURTHER DEVELOP ITS PRINCIPLES, AND LEARN MORE BESIDES FROM DOCTORS IN THE MIDDLE-EAST. THEY WILL LATER BECOME KNOWN AS THE KNIGHTS OF RHODES, THE KNIGHTS OF MALTA, AND TODAY, AS THE SOVEREIGN MILITARY ORDER OF MALTA (SMOM). IT IS AN

INDEPENDENT STATE OUTSIDE THE UN WITH NO OFFICIAL TERRITORY, BEYOND ITS MANY LAND HOLDINGS. YET IT HAS DIPLOMATIC RELATIONS WITH MANY COUNTRIES, OBSERVER STATUS AT THE UN, AND THE FACILITY TO ISSUE PASSPORTS TO ITS MEMBERS, WHO ARE ALL DRAWN FROM THE CHRISTIAN, USUALLY EUROPEAN, NOBILITY.

1119 CE: UGO DI PAGANI (KNOWN AS HUGUES DE PAYENS, OR IN ENGLISH, 'HUGH OF THE PAGANS', PAGANI BEING A TOWN IN SOUTHERN ITALY, ONCE INHABITED BY PAGANS), CN, FOUNDS THE ORDER OF THE POOR KNIGHTS OF CHRIST AND OF THE TEMPLE OF SOLOMON, ALSO KNOWN AS THE KNIGHTS TEMPLAR, A CN FRONT ORGANISATION DESIGNED TO BE A COVERTLY ROMAN MILITARY ORGANISATION, UNDER THE GUISE OF A RELIGIOUS ORDER OF WARRIOR-MONKS. THEY ARE MODELLED ON THE KNIGHTS OF ST JOHN, AND ARE LIKEWISE ONLY OPEN TO THE NOBILITY. THEY ARE EXEMPTED FROM TAXES, AND LOCAL LAW EXCEPT ROMAN LAW IN 1139, WHEN INNOCENT 2 OF ROME PUBLICLY CONFIRMS THEIR EXISTENCE. THOUGH THE CRUSADES ARE USED AS A PRETENCE TO JUSTIFY THEIR FOUNDATION AND CONTINUED EXISTENCE, 90% OF THEIR PERSONNEL ARE NON-COMBATTANT AND USE THEIR STATUS TO PASS ALL BORDERS UNCHALLENGED, ESTABLISH AND DEVELOP BUSINESS, BANKING AND A FINANCIAL NETWORK AND INFRASTRUCTURE, AS WELL AS 1000 ESTATES, ACROSS EUROPE AND THE MIDDLE-EAST. THEY GENERATE GREAT REVENUE FOR THE CN AND

ITS FURTHER OPERATIONS. PAGANI, INCIDENTALLY, IS CLOSE TO THE AMALFITAN COAST, IN ITALY. GERARDO SASSO (CN), THE FIRST GRANDMASTER OF THE KNIGHTS OF ST JOHN, WAS ALSO FROM AMALFI. IT IS LIKELY THEY WERE BOTH WORKING WITH BYZANTINE EMPIRE INTELLIGENCE.

1184 CE: LUCIUS 3 OF ROME (CN) ESTABLISHES THE ROMAN INQUISITION IN LANGUEDOC, TO PERSECUTE ALL OPPOSITION UNDER A CATHOLIC, RELIGIOUS, DISGUISE, LEADING TO THE ALBIGENSIAN GENOCIDE (1209–1229). IN 1229 THEY ESTABLISH IT PERMANENTLY AND IT SPREADS THROUGHOUT EUROPE. IT IS STAFFED BY CN AGENTS WITHIN THE DOMINICAN AND FRANCISCAN ORDERS, TWO CN FRONT ORGANISATIONS USED TO PENETRATE THE WIDER EUROPEAN COMMUNITY. AFTER 1200, A GRAND INQUISITOR SHALL HEAD EACH INQUISITION. SUSPECTS ARE ARRESTED, DETAINED AND TORTURED WITH CN TORTURE EQUIPMENT INTO GIVING CONFESSIONS. THEY ARE OFTEN BURNT ALIVE. OFFICIAL CONFESSIONS TO NON-RELIGIOUS BEHAVIOURS ARE PRODUCED FOR THE BENEFIT OF THOSE OUTSIDE THE CN, TO JUSTIFY THE INQUISITION'S EXISTENCE. THE TERM, 'INQUISITION', DESCRIBES ANY COURT PROCESS BASED ON ROMAN LAW. IN 1252, INNOCENT 4 OF ROME SHALL EXPLICITLY AUTHORIZE THE USE OF TORTURE TO ELICIT CONFESSIONS, AND BY 1256 INQUISITORS SHALL BE GIVEN 'ABSOLUTION' DESPITE USING TORTURE INSTRUMENTS. MANY MILLIONS SHALL BE

AFFECTED BY THE PERSECUTIONS BY THE CN OF ROME OVER THE CENTURIES TO COME, AND SHALL BE PARTICULARLY BRUTAL IN POST AL-ANDALUS SPAIN AFTER LA RECONQUISTA, WHERE JEWS, MUSLIMS AND OTHERS SHALL BE ARRESTED AND TORTURED AS POTENTIAL RESISTANCE TO THE CN, AND TRASTAMARA AND HABSBURG (BOTH CN ALLIES) RULE, AND FORCED TO CONVERT TO CATHOLIC CHRISITANITY TO AVOID PERSECUTION. THE DOMINICAN FRIAR TOMAS DE TORQUEMADA (CN), FIRST INQUISITOR GENERAL, SHALL BE PARTICULARLY INFAMOUS AS ONE OF THE WORST TORTURERS IN HISTORY. ALTHOUGH THE TREATY OF 1491 AGREED BETWEEN THE DEFEATED MUHAMMAD 12 OF AL-ANDALUS AND THE HOUSE OF TRASTAMARA SHALL GUARANTEE RELIGIOUS FREEDOM, IN 1492 THE TRASTAMARA SHALL DECREE THE EXPULSION OF ALL THOSE OF THE JEWISH FAITH, GIVING THEM ONLY FOUR MONTHS TO LEAVE THEIR ANCESTRAL HOME IN SPAIN FOR SAFE BUT FOREIGN COUNTRIES, TAKING WITH THEM NO VALUABLE POSESSIONS AT ALL, BUT LEAVING ANY WEALTH THEY MIGHT HAVE TO THE NEW AUTHORITIES. 200,000 SHALL LEAVE FOR FOREIGN COUNTRIES TO MAKE WAY FOR CN ALLIED CONQUERORS WHO PRACTICE ETHNIC CLEANSING. THOSE THAT REMAIN SHALL BE KNOWN AS 'CONVERSOS' (CASTILLIAN, NOW CALLED SPANISH, FOR 'CONVERTED') AND 'NUEVOS CRISTIANOS' (SPANISH FOR 'NEW CHRISTIANS'). EX-MUSLIMS SHALL BE PEJORATIVELY CALLED 'MORISCOS' (SPANISH FOR 'MOORISH', A REFERENCE TO THEIR OFTEN NORTH AFRICAN APPEARANCE), AND EX-JEWS, 'MARRANOS'

(OLD SPANISH FOR 'PIGS'), A REFERENCE TO THEIR NOT EATING PORK, A SIGN THAT THEY STILL HOLD TO JEWISH DIETARY RULES AND PRACTICES, AND ARE THUS NOT GENUINE CHRISTIANS, AND ALSO TO THE CHARACTERISTIC DIRTY, MUDDY APPEARANCE OF PIGS, OFTEN CALLED 'DIRTY ANIMALS', BEING A RACIST REFERENCE TO THEIR DARKER SKIN COLOUR. THEY SHALL ALWAYS BE UNDER SUSPICION BY THE AUTHORITIES REGARDLESS OF THEIR CONVERSION, AND MANY SHALL BE FORCED TO LEAVE ANYWAY. GRAND INQUISITIONS SHALL PERSIST UNTIL THE MID-19TH CENTURY, WITH THE INQUISITION EVENTUALLY BECOMING SUBSUMED INTO THE DICASTERY FOR THE DOCTRINE OF THE FAITH.

1213 CE: KING JOHN OF ENGLAND'S PERILOUS FINANCIAL AND MILITARY POSITION, BROUGHT ABOUT BY THE ACTIONS OF HIS BROTHER, KING RICHARD, COMBINED WITH CN INTRIGUES, FORCES HIM TO SURRENDER THE KINGDOM OF ENGLAND AND LORDSHIP OF IRELAND TO INNOCENT 3 OF ROME (CN) AND HE AGREES TO PAY ROME A FEUDAL RENT OF 700 AND 300 MARKS ANNUALLY, RESPECTIVELY, IN ORDER TO CONTINUE TO RULE, BUT NOW AS A VASSAL OF ROME. ROME NOW HAS OFFICIAL TERRITORY IN BOTH ITALY AND THE BRITISH ISLES.

1307 - 1312 CE: CLEMENT V OF ROME (CN) IS PRESSURED BY PHILLIP 4 OF FRANCE TO ALLOW THE ARREST OF THE KNIGHTS TEMPLARS. IT WAS A CN FRONT

ORGANISATION CREATED AS A REACTION/ANTITHESIS TO THE 'CRUSADES', A CN PLANNED PROBLEM/THESIS. IT CONSTITUTED A ROMAN MILITARY CELL, SIMILAR TO THE KNIGHTS OF ST JOHN (CN CELL), WHICH WAS PLANNING A EUROPE-WIDE REVOLUTION TO OVERTHROW PHILLIP 4 AND OTHERS. MANY ARE TORTURED, TRIED AND BURNED AT THE STAKE, BUT THEY HAD ALREADY GAINED MANY LAND HOLDINGS ACROSS EUROPE AND GREATLY PROFITED FROM USURY. THEIR HOLDINGS PASSED TO THE KNIGHTS OF ST JOHN, AND MANY ARE SAID TO HAVE ENTERED THE ORDER OF CHRIST IN PORTUGAL, AND PERHAPS THE JEWISH COMMUNITY IN GERMANY (UNDER THE PROTECTION OF THE TEUTONIC ORDER), FEIGNING CONVERSION IN ORDER TO CONTINUE TO PRACTICE MONEY LENDING AS MIDDLEMEN FOR THE CN, AS THEY HAD AS THE KNIGHTS TEMPLARS.

1308 CE: THE ORDER OF BROTHERS OF THE GERMAN HOUSE OF ST MARY IN JERUALEM, OTHERWISE KNOWN AS THE TEUTONIC ORDER/TEUTONIC KNIGHTS, A CN FRONT ORGANISATION, CONTINUE THEIR CONQUEST, BEGUN IN THE 12TH CENTURY CE, OF LANDS WHICH SHALL EVENTUALLY BECOME THE MODERN STATE OF PRUSSIA.

1371 CE: THE CN TAKE OVER A PROSPEROUS SCOTLAND. A BARONIAL REVOLT LED BY HIS TREACHEROUS HIGH STEWARD (HEAD OF ROYAL HOUSEHOLD), ROBERT STEWART (CN), LEADS TO THE

DEATH OF DAVID 2 OF SCOTLAND AND THE REPLACEMENT OF THE BRUCE DYNASTY BY THE STEWARTS (CN).

1453 CE: WHAT REMAINS OF THE EASTERN ROMAN, CALLED BYZANTINE, EMPIRE, IS CONQUERED BY SULTAN MEHMET 2 AFTER CENTURIES OF TERRITORIAL ATTRITION, WITH THE FALL OF CONSTANTINOPLE.

1525 CE: ALBERT HOHENZOLLERN (CN), GRAND MASTER OF THE TEUTONIC ORDER, RESIGNS HIS POSITION AND BECOMES DUKE ALBERT 1 OF PRUSSIA. THIS ENABLES HIM TO BECOME A TEMPORAL RULER, MARRY AND PRODUCE LEGITIMATE HEIRS, AND BUILD UP A POWER BASE IN THE AREA.

1536 - 1603 CE: THE GUILDS WERE SUPPRESSED, ALONG WITH MONASTERIES, IN ENGLAND BY HENRY 8 OF ENGLAND. GUILDS OF MASONRY, THE ART OF BUILDING WITH STONE, HOWEVER, HAD EXISTED UNDER CHURCH CONTROL, UP UNTIL THE REFORMATION IN ENGLAND. THE SPREAD OF PROTESTANTISM THEN LED TO A SLOW-DOWN IN CHURCH BUILDING, AND MANY MASONS FOUND THEMSELVES FINANCIALLY INCONVENIENCED, LEADING TO RESENTMENT. WHILE SUPPRESSED IN ENGLAND, THE GUILDS IN SCOTLAND CARRIED ON AS BEFORE, ALONG WITH A PRESENCE IN IRELAND AND THE CITY OF LONDON, BEYOND TUDOR CONTROL.

THIS LED TO NETWORKS OF MASONS, WHOSE OPEN AND SECRET GATHERINGS WOULD PROVE FERTILE RECRUITMENT GROUNDS FOR CN SPIES, PARTICULARLY WITHIN THE SUPPRESSED KNIGHTS OF ST JOHN, AND CHURCH ORDERS, INCLUDING THE JESUITS AFTER 1540 CE.

THEY ADOPTED THE TITLE, 'FREEMASONS', FOR THEIR SECRET GROUP WITHIN GROUPS OF MASONS. THIS WAS A REFERENCE TO FREE WILL, A CORE TENET OF CATHOLIC BELIEF, AS OPPOSED TO THE PREDESTINATION PREACHED BY PROTESTANT REFORMERS, AND WAS INCLUDED TO ASSIST THE CN IN THE RECRUITMENT OF CATHOLICS FOR CN PURPOSES, WHILST THEY MASQUERADED AS RELIGIOUS, CATHOLIC PRIESTS AND SPIES. FREEMASONRY'S FIRST PUBLICLY KNOWN LODGE, KNOWN AS LODGE CANONGATE KILWINNING, WOULDN'T MEET, IN ST MARY'S CHAPEL, EDINBURGH, UNTIL 1677 CE.

IN THOSE DAYS, TRAVEL WAS TIGHTLY RESTRICTED, AND MANY DIDN'T VENTURE OUTSIDE THEIR VILLAGE OR FARM ANYWAY. ONLY CERTAIN SECTIONS OF SOCIETY WOULD TRAVEL, SUCH AS THE NOBILITY, CLERGY AND THOSE THAT WORKED FOR THEM, INCLUDING CRAFTSMEN ON THEIR WAY TO A BUILDING SITE. THEY COULD EXPECT TO BE STOPPED ON THE ROAD AT CHECK POINTS, WHERE SOLDIERS WOULD ASK THE TRAVELLER FOR PAPERWORK TO

PROVE THEIR IDENTITY, LOCATION OF DEPARTURE AND DESTINATION, AND THEIR RIGHT TO TRAVEL. A PERSON COULD DRESS AS A MASON, WITH FORGED PAPERWORK, AS A MEANS TO TRAVEL WITHOUT AROUSING SUSPICION AS TO THEIR TRUE IDENTITY AND MOTIVES. A STEWART SUPPORTING NOBLE ONCE WROTE A LETTER TO A FELLOW SUPPORTER, IN WHICH HE MENTIONED, IN THIS CONNECTION, 'PLAYING THE MASON'.

THE CN WOULD USE THIS SECRET GROUP OF CATHOLICS AND CN, TO UNDERMINE THE STATE SO THAT THEY COULD PLACE A CN, UNDER THE GUISE OF PLACING A CATHOLIC, RULER ON THE THRONE OF ENGLAND. THAT RULER WOULD BE JAMES 1 OF ENGLAND (CN).

1540 CE: THE MILITARY ORDER OF THE SOCIETY OF JESUS (JESUITS) IS CREATED BY IGNATIUS DE LOYOLA (CN) AND PAUL 3 OF ROME (CN). IT WAS, AND STILL IS, A MILITANT CN FRONT ORGANISATION AND CELL DESIGNED TO RESTORE WANING CONFIDENCE IN ROME, COMPETE WITH NEW COMPETITORS FOR INFLUENCE, INFILTRATE COMMUNITIES AND CREATE AN EXTENSIVE BUSINESS AND SPY NETWORK.

1566 CE: THE CN CREATE 'THE ENTITY', THROUGH THEIR CONTROL OF THE VATICAN. IT SHALL BE USED AS A SPECIAL VATICAN SECRET SERVICE AGENCY,

TASKED WITH PURSUING CN GOALS SUCH AS INFILTRATION.

1603 CE: AFTER A BRIEF INTERLUDE OF TUDOR RULE, JAMES 6 OF SCOTLAND (CN) TAKES OVER THE MONARCHY OF ENGLAND AND IRELAND, WHERE HE BECOMES KNOWN AS JAMES 1, UNITING THE 3 CROWNS. HE IS THE DESCENDANT OF ROBERT STEWART (CN), THE TREACHEROUS SERVANT AND MURDERER OF HIS KING, DAVID 2. THE CN NOW CONTROLS THE MONARCHIES OF ALL THREE AREAS OF THE BRITISH ISLES, THOUGH THEY HAVE TO CONTEND WITH THE BRITISH ARISTOCRACY AND PEOPLE, MANY OF WHOM DO NOT KNOW OF JAMES STEWART'S SECRET ALLEGIANCE TO THE CN OF ROME.

1605 CE: THE CN STAGE A FALSE FLAG ATTACK CALLED 'THE GUNPOWDER PLOT', BUT MAKE SURE TO FOIL IT BEFORE IT CAN REACH CONCLUSION. IT IS DONE TO MAKE IT APPEAR TO THE BRITISH ARISTOCRACY AND PEOPLE, THAT JAMES STEWART (CN) IS AN ENEMY OF ROME, WHO THE CN MAKE SURE TO BLAME FOR THE PLOT. THUS, HIS ANTI-ROME CREDENTIALS NOW APPEAR ABOVE SUSPICION.

1660 CE: CHARLES 2 (CN) IS RESTORED TO THE THRONE OF ENGLAND, SCOTLAND AND IRELAND, FOLLOWING THE END OF THE COMMONWEALTH OF ENGLAND, SET UP FOLLOWING THE EXECUTION OF HIS FATHER CHARLES 1 (CN) IN 1649 CE.

1688 CE: JAMES 2 (CN) OF ENGLAND, 7 OF SCOTLAND AND IRELAND, BROTHER OF CHARLES 2 OF ENGLAND (CN), DEPOSED BY WILLIAM OF ORANGE, WHO BECOMES WILLIAM 3 OF ENGLAND IN 1689 CE. AFTER ATTEMPTING TO DEFEND HIS CROWN, JAMES 2 GOES INTO EXILE IN FRANCE, AT THE INVITATION OF THE KING OF FRANCE, LOUIS 14. HIS JACOBITE (JACOBITEAN) SERVICE SOON ESTABLISH A PRESENCE IN FRANCE.

1714 CE: THE ELECTOR OF HANNOVER (CN), A DESCENDANT OF JAMES 1 (CN), TAKES BACK THE MONARCHIES OF ENGLAND, SCOTLAND AND IRELAND, FOR THE CN, FOLLOWING THE DEATHS OF ANNE 1 OF ENGLAND AND HIS MOTHER, SOPHIA. HE RULES AS GEORGE 1 OF GREAT BRITAIN. THE CN NOW CONTROLS BRITAIN AGAIN, NOW AS A UNITED KINGDOM, AFTER THE ACTS OF UNION OF 1706 CE AND 1707 CE. THE HOUSE OF HANNOVER DESCEND FROM THE HOUSE OF WELF. WELF IS A GERMAN VARIANT OF 'GUELPH'. THE GUELFS WERE ALLIED WITH CN INTERESTS, OPPOSING THE EMPEROR. THROUGH THE WELF FAMILY, GEORGE 1 DEFENDS FROM THE D'ESTE FAMILY OF VENETO, AND IT IS SAID, A FAMILY OF ROME, THAT LED THE DEFENSE OF ROME AGAINST ODOACER, KNOWN AS ATTI, ATIA OR ATTIA. IN ADDITION TO BEING CN MEMBERS, THEY ARE SAID TO BE DESCENDED FROM A BLACK NOBILITY FAMILY.

1715 CE: THE '15, OTHERWISE KNOWN AS 'THE JACOBITE RISING OF 1715 CE', WAS A PHONY WAR FOUGHT BETWEEN CN CONTROLLED HANNOVERIAN FORCES, AND CN CONTROLLED JACOBITE FORCES FIGHTING FOR JAMES EDWARD STUART (CORRUPTION OF STEWARD/STEWART), CN, THE 'OLD PRETENDER, AND KNOWN AS JAMES 3 OF ENGLAND ACCORDING TO THE JACOBITE SUCCESSION. IT WAS DONE TO PERPETUATE THE IDEA THAT THE HANNOVERIAN MONARCHY WAS RELIGIOUSLY CHRISTIAN AND PROTESTANT, NOT CATHOLIC. IN FACT, IT WAS NEITHER, BUT INSTEAD CN CONTROLLED (LOYAL TO ROME). FOR HIS PART, JAMES EDWART STUART WANTED TO PERPETUATE THE IDEA THAT HE WAS A TRUE CATHOLIC, AND ACTIVELY ENGAGED UPON TRYING TO TAKE BACK THE THRONE OF ENGLAND, LOST IN 1688 CE, FOR THE STUART FAMILY AND CATHOLICISM. THIS WAS IMPORTANT, IN ORDER THAT HE MIGHT JUSTIFY HIS CONTINUED RESIDENCE IN FRANCE TO THE KING OF FRANCE, LOUIS 14.

1717 CE: THE PREMIER GRAND LODGE OF LONDON (THE FIRST FREEMASONIC GRAND LODGE IN THE WORLD) OF FREE AND ACCEPTED MASONS IS SET UP IN LONDON, WITH CN APPROVAL AND ASSISTANCE. AS A SOCIAL CLUB WHICH MANY EDUCATED, SKILLED AND WEALTHY PEOPLE ATTEND, IT PROVES USEFUL TO THE CN AS A NETWORK OF USEFUL PEOPLE FROM WHICH THE CN CAN RECRUIT MEMBERS, AND CN MEMBERS CAN ALSO INFLUENCE THEIR FREEMASONIC BRETHREN DUE TO FREEMASONRY'S RANKING

SYSTEM, WHICH CAN PLACE LOWER RANKING BRETHREN UNDER CN FREEMASONS' INFLUENCE. UNDER GEORGE 1, CLUBS SUDDENLY PROLIFERATE, AND LODGES ARE AMONG MANY OTHER CLUBS DURING THE GEORGIAN CLUB CRAZE, ALL OF WHICH CAN ALSO BE USED AS RECRUITMENT POOLS. THE PREMIER GRAND LODGE IS THE FIRST BRITISH INSTITUTION TO ALLOW THOSE OF THE JEWISH, AND OTHER FAITHS TO JOIN. IT PROVES USEFUL PROPAGANDA FOR THE PURPOSES OF SHOWING ITSELF TO BE A PROGRESSIVE AND TOLERANT INSTITUTION. HOWEVER, IT ALSO ENABLES THE CN TO MAKE NEW CONNECTIONS WITHIN THE JEWISH COMMUNITY. MUSLIM AMBASSADORS FROM COUNTRIES OUTSIDE EUROPE ALSO JOIN, FACILITATING CN CONTACT WITH THEIR GOVERNMENTS. 'ACCEPTED' IS A REFERENCE TO THE 'ACCEPTION' (ACCEPTANCE) OF NON-MASONS, VIZ GENTLEMEN, INTO AN ORGANISATION WHICH TRACED ITS HISTORY TO MASONS' GUILDS.

ITS RITUALS ARE WRITTEN BY THE JESUIT ORDER (CN). THE CN SPY, JAMES ANDERSON, WRITES 'THE CONSTITUTIONS OF THE FREEMASONS' IN 1723 CE, ALLEGING A FICTIONAL HISTORY OF THE ORDER (FOUNDATION MYTH) TO GIVE IT GREATER PRESTIGE IN ORDER TO ATTRACT NEW MEMBERS. ON THE TITLE PAGE, AN ILLUSTRATION SHOWS THE ROMAN EAGLE, STANDING TRIUMPHANTLY AND SPREADING ITS WINGS, ABOVE A LION, TO ITS RIGHT, AND A UNICORN, TO ITS LEFT, REPRESENTING THE KINGDOMS OF ENGLAND AND SCOTLAND, RESPECTIVELY.

ORDINARILY THE SUPPORTERS OF THE ROYAL ARMS OF THE KINGDOM OF GREAT BRITAIN, THE LION AND THE UNICORN ARE DISPLAYED IN THIS WAY IN SCOTLAND, BUT IN ENGLAND THE LION IS ON THE LEFT, WITH THE UNICORN ON THE RIGHT. THIS MIGHT BE A REFERENCE TO THE SCOTTISH ORIGINS, OF JAMES 1 OF ENGLAND WHO WAS GEORGE 1'S ANCESTOR, AND OF FREEMASONRY, FIRST INSTITUTED BY THE JESUIT ORDER (CN) IN SCOTLAND, IT IS THOUGHT. ON THE ROYAL COAT OF ARMS OF SCOTLAND, THE SUPPORTERS ARE RAMPANT AND TURNED INWARDS, THEIR BODIES INCLINED FORWARDS, TO SUPPORT THE ESCUTCHEON. IN THE ILLUSTRATION THEY ARE SHOWN TURNED OUTWARDS, THEIR BODIES INCLINED AWAY FROM THE EAGLE, YET WITH THEIR HEADS LOOKING BACK AND UP AT THE EAGLE, AS IF THEY ARE COWERING IN AWE. THIS SYMBOLISES THE DOMINANCE OF ROME OVER ENGLAND AND SCOTLAND AND THE AWE AND FEAR THE CN STRIKE INTO THE HEARTS OF THE PEOPLE OF THOSE KINGDOMS. THE SCOTTISH ARRANGEMENT OF THE SUPPORTERS ALSO BRINGS TO MIND THE MOTTO OF THE SCOTTISH CROWN: 'NEMO ME IMPUNE LACESSIT', WHICH IN ENGLISH MEANS, 'NO ONE PROVOKES ME WITH IMPUNITY'. CN SPIES SUCH AS ELIAS ASHMOLE, AN EXPERT IN HERALDRY, ARE THOUGHT TO HAVE BEEN CRYPTO-JESUIT PRIESTS, WHICH WOULD EXPLAIN WHY THE TITLE PAGE REFERS TO THE FREEMASONS AS 'THAT MOST ANCIENT AND RIGHT WORSHIPFUL FRATERNITY', 'MOST ANCIENT' BEING A CODE FOR ANCIENT ROME AND 'WORSHIPFUL FRATERNITY' A CODE FOR THE ROMAN PRIESTHOOD.

FREEMASONRY LATER ADOPTS A PUBLIC CHARITABLE FUNCTION AND IMAGE, WHICH SERVES TO DEFLECT CRITICISM OF IT AS A SEMI-SECRET GROUP. THE PREMIER GRAND LODGE OF LONDON BECOMES THE GRAND LODGE OF ENGLAND IN 1738 CE, AND FURTHER GRAND LODGES ARE SET UP IN OTHER PARTS OF THE UK. THE GROWTH OF THE CN CONTROLLED BRITISH EMPIRE FRONT ORGANISATION, ABROAD, ENABLES RECRUITMENT WITHIN NEWLY CONQUERED CN CONTROLLED TERRITORIES, WORLD-WIDE.

1728 CE: CN AGENTS AMONG THE JACOBITE EXILES SET UP THE GRAND LODGE OF FRANCE IN PARIS. THEIR AIM IS TO UNDERMINE SUPPORT FOR LOUIS 15, WITH A VIEW TO REPLACING HIS FAMILY WITH CN AGENTS, TO TAKE OVER FRANCE AND ITS EMPIRE. THEY HAD BEEN SETTING UP LODGES AND BUILDING TOWARDS A GRAND LODGE SINCE 1725 CE, AND AS EARLY AS THEIR ARRIVAL IN 1688 CE, ACCORDING TO SOME SOURCES. THEY RECRUIT MANY FRENCHMEN INTO FREEMASONRY, AND ALSO INTO THE CN. OVER THE COMING DECADES, THEY CREATE NEW CHIVALRIC DEGREES AIMED AT ATTRACTING THE FRENCH ARISTOCRACY INTO FREEMASONRY AND ALSO THE CN. THEY START TO BUILD TOWARDS A GENERAL UPRISING. IT IS SUSPECTED THAT WILLIAM 3 OF ENGLAND MIGHT HAVE HIMSELF, BEEN A CN AGENT, AND HIS CONFLICT WITH JAMES 2, STAGED. JAMES 2 OF ENGLAND'S FLIGHT TO FRANCE COULD HAVE BEEN

ENGINEERED BY CN TO SET UP A SPY NETWORK WITHIN FRANCE WITH A VIEW TO TAKING OVER FRANCE. THIS WOULD SET THE STAGE FOR THE OSTENSIBLY PROTESTANT GEORGE 1'S HOUSE OF HANNOVER TO TAKE OVER THE BRITISH MONARCHY, AND APPEAR ABOVE SUSPICION DURING THE PHONY JACOBITE REBELLIONS PERIOD, AFTER THE BRITISH THRONE PASSED TO THEM FROM ANNE STUART, HERSELF SUSPECTEDLY CN, HAVING INHERITED IT FROM WILLIAM 3.

1737 CE: FREEMASONRY IS OUTLAWED IN FRANCE BY LOUIS 15, AFTER POLICE REPORTS THROW SUSPICION ON THE ORGANISATION. THE LODGES CONTINUE TO MEET CLANDESTINELY.

1745 CE: THE '45, OTHERWISE KNOWN AS 'THE JACOBITE RISING OF 1745 CE', WAS A PHONY WAR FOUGHT BETWEEN CN CONTROLLED HANNOVERIAN FORCES, AND CN CONTROLLED JACOBITE FORCES FIGHTING FOR CHARLES EDWARD STUART (CN), OTHERWISE KNOWN AS BONNIE PRINCE CHARLIE, ON BEHALF OF HIS FATHER, JAMES EDWARD STUART (CN). IT WAS DONE TO PERPETUATE THE IDEA THAT THE HANNOVERIAN MONARCHY WAS RELIGIOUSLY CHRISTIAN AND PROTESTANT, NOT CATHOLIC. IN FACT, IT WAS NEITHER, BUT INSTEAD CN CONTROLLED (LOYAL TO ROME). FOR THEIR PART, JAMES AND CHARLES STUART WANTED TO PERPETUATE THE IDEA THAT THEY WERE TRUE

CATHOLICS, AND ACTIVELY ENGAGED UPON TRYING TO TAKE BACK THE THRONE OF ENGLAND, LOST IN 1688 CE, FOR THE STUART FAMILY AND CATHOLICISM. THIS WAS IMPORTANT, IN ORDER THAT THEY MIGHT JUSTIFY THEIR FORMER RESIDENCE IN FRANCE TO THE KING OF FRANCE, LOUIS 15, AND THEREBY PLACE THEMSELVES ABOVE SUSPICION. WILLIAM ST. CLAIR, 20TH BARON OF ROSLIN, WAS FIRST GRAND MASTER OF THE GRAND LODGE OF SCOTLAND IN 1736 CE, AND IT IS SUSPECTED, CN. THE ST. CLAIR FAMILY HAD SUPPORTED THE JACOBITE CAUSE IN 1715 CE, BUT IN 1745 CE THEY CHOSE TO SIDE WITH GEORGE 2 OF ENGLAND INSTEAD, DESPITE THEIR JACOBITE SYMPATHIES.

1773 CE: SUPPRESSION OF THE JESUIT ORDER (CN) BY THE POPE, AFTER CONDEMNATION OF THE ORDER BY THE KINGS OF FRANCE, SPAIN, AND OTHERS. THEY FIND SAFE HAVEN IN HOHENZOLLERN (CN) CONTROLLED PRUSSIA AND AT THE COURT OF CATHERINE, TSARINA OF RUSSIA (CN). RUSSIA, RULED BY A TSAR OR TSARINA, HAD DEVELOPED AS A BYZANTINE SATELLITE STATE BEFORE THE FALL OF CONSTANTINOPLE IN 1453. CONSTANTINOPLE HAD BEEN KNOWN AS THE SECOND ROME. AFTER 1453, MOSCOW WOULD BECOME KNOWN AS THE THIRD ROME, WITH BYZANTINE REFUGEES JOINING THE PRO-BYZANTINE ESTABLISHMENT IN RUSSIA. THE WORLD 'TSAR', IN RUSSIAN, LIKE THE WORD 'KAISER', IN GERMAN, MEANS 'CAESAR', A ROMAN IMPERIAL TITLE. BOTH THE HOHENZOLLERNS OF THE LATTER GERMAN

EMPIRE, AND THE ROMANOV'S OF THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE, ADOPTED IT. THEY WOULD ALSO BOTH ADOPT THE BYZANTINE DOUBLE-HEADED EAGLE AS A SYMBOL, SIGNIFYING THE UNION OF THE WESTERN AND EASTERN ROMAN EMPIRES. THIS SYMBOL IS ALSO A MASONIC SCOTTISH RITE SYMBOL, AND THE TITLE OF 'THE KNIGHT OF THE EAST AND WEST' DEGREE, REFERS TO THE ROMAN EMPIRE

1776 CE: CRYPTO-JESUIT AND CN AGENT ADAM WEISHAAPT CREATES A NEW CN FRONT ORGANISATION TO REPLACE THE JESUITS WITHIN FREEMASONRY, AND FUNCTION IN THE SAME WAY AS THE JESUITS HAD DONE, WITHIN FREEMASONRY. HE FIRST CALLED IT 'THE PERFECTIBILISTS', THEN LATER, 'THE ILLUMINATI'. IT IS SUSPECTED THAT AFTER A CONGRESS AT WILHELMSBAD IN 1782 CE, THE ILLUMINATI HAD SUCH ADHERENCE WITHIN CONTINENTAL FREEMASONRY THAT IT BECAME THE DOMINANT FORCE WITHIN IT FROM 1782 CE ONWARDS. IT HAD MANY WELL KNOWN MEMBERS, SUCH AS EUROPEAN ARISTOCRATS AND INTELLECTUALS SUCH AS JOHANN WOLFGANG VON GOETHE. AFTER ITS DISCOVERY AND SUPPRESSION BY CHARLES THEODORE, ELECTOR OF BAVARIA, IN 1785 CE, DOCUMENTS AND INTERNAL CORRESPONDENCE, SEIZED IN 1786 CE AND 1787 CE, WERE SUBSEQUENTLY PUBLISHED BY THE BAVARIAN GOVERNMENT IN 1787 CE, REVEALING AN INTERNATIONAL CONSPIRACY. BY THAT TIME, HOWEVER, THE ILLUMINATI HAD

ESTABLISHED THEMSELVES IN EUROPEAN LODGES, AND IN FRANCE IN PARTICULAR.

1776 CE: THE KINGDOM OF GREAT BRITAIN'S GOVERNMENT, LOYAL TO GEORGE 3 OF GREAT BRITAIN (CN), CREATE A COMPANY NAMED 'UNITED STATES OF AMERICA' TO RUN THE AFFAIRS OF SOME OF THEIR NORTH AMERICAN COLONIAL POSSESSIONS. THIS IS DONE TO REMOVE CONTROL OF THOSE COLONIES FROM THE BRITISH PARLIAMENT, AND THROUGH IT THE BRITISH ARISTOCRACY, LANDED GENTRY AND BRITISH SUBJECTS, GENERALLY. THE CN EMPLOY BRITISH ARMY GENERAL GEORGE WASHINGTON (CN), POSTMASTER GENERAL (SPY POSITION) BENJAMIN FRANKLYN (CN), ALEXANDER HAMILTON, (CN) AND OTHERS, TO CREATE AN ILLUSION, LATER CALLED 'THE AMERICAN REVOLUTION' AND 'THE WAR OF INDEPENDENCE'. MANY DISSIDENTS AND POTENTIAL DISSIDENTS ARE KILLED, ARRESTED AND EXPROPRIATED. WASHINGTON BRINGS IN MILITARY RULE DISGUISED AS A REPRESENTATIVE DEMOCRACY, IN WHICH ELECTIONS ARE CONTESTED BETWEEN CAREFULLY CHOSEN CN SPIES AND CONFIDANTES, AND RIGGED TO PRODUCE THE DESIRED RESULT: CN RULE. THE CN CONTROLLED HANNOVERIAN, NOW CALLED WINDSOR, GOVERNMENT SHALL CARRY ON RUNNING THE UNITED STATES IN SECRET UNTIL THE PRESENT DAY, AND FOLLOWING ITS SUCCESS, ADOPT THE STRATEGY FOR OTHER CRYPTO-CN COLONIES. A SIDE-BENEFIT OF THIS STRATEGY IS THAT THE PEOPLE OF

THE USA BELIEVE THEMSELVES TO BE FREE, AND SO DO NOT REVOLT AGAINST RULE FROM LONDON, THOUGH THEY ARE RULED MORE HARSHLY THAN BEFORE. THEIR CRYPTO-HANNOVER GOVERNMENT IS LEGALLY CALLED AN ADMINISTRATION, NOT A GOVERNMENT, AS IT IS THE ADMINISTRATION OF A COMPANY, OWNED BY THE CROWN. IN USA COURT ROOMS A GOLD-FRINGED FLAG MUST FLY, AS THE USA IS LEGALLY A NAVAL COLONY. THEY MAINTAIN ENGLISH COMMON LAW AS THEIR LEGAL SYSTEM, BY WHICH THEIR 'DECLARATION OF INDEPENDENCE' IS ILLEGAL. THE LEGALITY OF THIS SITUATION SHALL REMAIN UNCHALLENGED UNTIL THE ENTRANCE OF THE USA INTO THE LEAGUE OF NATIONS, AND THEN INTO THE UNITED NATIONS, WHOSE CHARTER SHALL STIPULATE THE RIGHT TO SELF-DETERMINATION OF PEOPLES OF THE UN, RENDERING COLONIES AND CRYPTO-COLONIES ILLEGAL AS PER INTERNATIONAL LAW, WHICH SHALL SUPERSEDE ENGLISH COMMON LAW. THE CN CONTROLLED UK, SUCCESSOR STATE TO THE CN CONTROLLED BRITISH EMPIRE, SHALL BE CAUTIOUS TO KEEP THIS INFORMATION A CLOSELY GUARDED SECRET, THROUGH A CAMPAIGN OF PUBLIC DISINFORMATION, IN ORDER TO AVOID LOSING CONTROL OF ITS COLONIAL/CORPORATE POSSESSIONS, WHICH IN 2023 SHALL INCLUDE THE USA, RUSSIAN FEDERATION, FEDERATIVE REPUBLIC OF BRAZIL, STATE OF ISRAEL, ISLAMIC REPUBLICS OF IRAN AND PAKISTAN, PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC OF CHINA AND MANY MORE. OFTEN THESE CN CONTROLLED STATES SHALL BE INDUCED BY THE CN TO PUBLICLY CONDEMN AND ATTACK EACH OTHER AND THE UK, IN ORDER TO

CREATE THE ILLUSION THAT THEY ARE FREE, WHEN IN FACT THEY ARE ALL SECRETLY CONTROLLED BY CN. THEY SHALL USE THIS ILLUSION TO FOOL OTHER STATES INTO BECOMING THEIR ALLIES, CREATING DIVISION. THE SCRIPTED POLITICAL INTRIGUES THEY ENGAGE IN SHALL BE USED TO START THE THIRD WORLD WAR PREDICTED BY ALBERT PIKE (CN), AFTER HOODWINKING THEIR ALLIES INTO JOINING THEIR RESPECTIVE CAUSES AND THUS CHOOSING A SIDE, AND DECLARING WAR THEMSELVES, AGAINST THEIR OWN INTERESTS, WITH THE INEVITABLE RESULT PREDICTED BY PIKE: GENOCIDE, CN DOMINATION AND THE OPEN REVELATION OF LUCIFERIANISM, THOUGHT TO BE SATANISM, THE ROMAN RELIGION OF WORSHIPPING ASMODEUS, PRINCE OF DEMONS, WHICH WOULD THEN BECOME THE NEW WORLD STATE RELIGION. IT SHALL BE THE CN THAT CREATES THE UN IN 1945, TO PREPARE THE GROUND FOR A WORLD GOVERNMENT AFTER THE THIRD WORLD WAR. WHEREAS THE ROMAN EMPIRE. BYZANTINE EMPIRE, BRITISH EMPIRE, SOVIET UNION, PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC OF CHINA, USA, FRENCH REPUBLIC AND RUSSIAN FEDERATION, ALL HAD, HAVE, OR SHALL HAVE RED, OR RED AND YELLOW, OR RED, BLUE AND WHITE (THE COLOURS OF A FLAME, A REFERENCE TO RITUAL SACRIFICE) AS THEIR COLOURS, THE UN SHALL ADOPT BLUE AND WHITE AS ITS COLOURS, A REFERENCE TO THE CONSPIRACY THEORY THAT JEWISH PEOPLE WIN THE SECOND WORLD WAR AFTER BEATING ADOLF HITLER WITH THEIR JEWISH CONTROLLED STATES. THE CN SHALL MAKE SURE THE CN CONTROLLED STATE OF ISRAEL SHALL ADOPT

THOSE COLOURS, TO REINFORCE THE IDEA IN PEOPLE'S, ESPECIALLY SYMBOLOGISTS' MINDS, THAT THE UN IS JEWISH, NOT CN, CONTROLLED. FOLLOWING THE THIRD WORLD WAR, ALL JEWS AND MUSLIMS SHALL HAVE BEEN KILLED, AND BLAMED FOR STARTING THE WAR. THE UN FLAG, IN ADDITION TO ITS ALREADY EXISTENT ROMAN LAURELS OF VICTORY, SHALL THEN ADOPT RED AND YELLOW COLOURING INSTEAD. EVENTUALLY, THE CN MIGHT ADD A ROMAN EAGLE, MAKING THE UN FLAG EVEN MORE SIMILAR TO THE ROMAN EMPIRE FLAG, OR POSSIBLY JUST REPLACE IT WITH THE ROMAN EMPIRE FLAG, MAKING THEIR FINAL VICTORY PUBLIC, FOR ALL THE WORLD TO SEE.

1789 CE: FOLLOWING THE COSTLY SEVEN YEARS WAR, FRENCH AND INDIAN WAR, AND THE LOSS OF NEW FRANCE TO GREAT BRITAIN, FRANCE HAS BEEN LOSING ITS STRUGGLE WITH GREAT BRITAIN FOR SUPREMACY. PRUSSIA IS ALSO STARTING TO DEVELOP SWIFTLY, SO FRANCE FACES INCREASING COMPETITION AND IS LESS ECONOMICALLY SUCCESSFUL THAN BEFORE. THE CN STAGE THEIR LONG-PLANNED UPRISING IN FRANCE, USING AGENTS WITHIN THE CN CLANDESTINE ORGANISATION, THE ILLUMINATI, AND THE JACOBIN CLUB CN FRONT ORGANISATION AS AGENTS PROVOCATEURS. THEY ARE NAMED 'JACOBINS' AS THEY ARE KNOWN TO MEET IN THE MONASTERY OF THE JACOBINS (NAME FOR THE FRENCH DOMICAN ORDER) IN THE RUE SAINT-HONORE, ADJACENT TO THE SEAT OF THE

ASSEMBLY. ANOTHER REASON MIGHT BE THAT THEY ARE OFTEN CLANDESTINE FREEMASONS, ESTABLISHED BY THE JACOBITES IN FRANCE. THE NAME 'JACQUES', WHICH TRANSLATES AS 'JAMES' OR 'JACOB' IN ENGLISH, 'IACOBUS' IN LATIN, AND 'YAAQOV' IN HEBREW, MEANS 'HEEL CATCHER', 'SUPPLANTER' AND 'LEG-PULLER'. IT CAN BE A REFERENCE TO THE BIBLICAL JACOB OF GENESIS 25:29-34, WHO BETRAYED HIS NAIVE AND HUNGRY BROTHER BY FOOLING HIM INTO SELLING HIM HIS BIRTHRIGHT FOR A MESS OF POTTAGE, AND EXPLOITED HIS FATHER ISAAC'S VULNERABILITY AS A BLIND AND AGED MAN, BY IMPERSONATING HIS BROTHER ESAU WHILE LYING TO HIM. THE REALISATION THEY HAD BEEN DECEIVED SHOCKED BOTH ISAAC AND ESAU, WHO WAS HEARTBROKEN BY HIS BROTHER'S TREACHERY AND HATED HIM FOR IT. THE JACOBINS ARE OFTEN FROM BRITTANY, WHERE SHIPS FROM GREAT BRITAIN CAN EASILY LAND AND BRING VARIOUS FORMS OF ASSISTANCE. THE CN HAVE RECRUITED MANY WITHIN THE FRENCH ESTABLISHMENT TO BETRAY LOUIS 16. THEY HAVE LAID THE GROUNDWORK FOR A REVOLUTION THROUGH A WHISPERING, DIRTY TRICKS AND BLACK PROPAGANDA CAMPAIGN AGAINST THE BOURBON MONARCHY TO MAKE IT UNPOPULAR. IN 1785, THE CN INSTIGATED AN INTRIGUE CALLED 'THE AFFAIR OF THE DIAMOND NECKLACE' TO DISCREDIT THE KING. THEY ALSO CREATED A FALSE RUMOUR THAT QUEEN MARIE-ANTOINETTE MOCKED THE HUNGRY OF FRANCE BY SAYING 'LET THEM EAT CAKE'. IN FACT, THE EXPRESSION COMES FROM 'CONFESSIONS' BY

JEAN-JACQUES ROUSSEAU WRITTEN IN 1767, REFERRING TO AN UNNAMED PRINCESSE, AND WAS MERELY ATTRIBUTED TO THE QUEEN TO MAKE HER UNPOPULAR. IT IS SUSPECTED THAT THE CN ORGANISE SOLDIERS DRESSED AS POOR PEOPLE, 'LES SANS-CULOTTES', TO PARTICIPATE IN THE INSURRECTION, AND THAT CN CONTROLLED AUXILLARY FORCES, SUCH AS MERCENARIES, FROM GREAT BRITAIN AND OTHER PARTS OF EUROPE, ARE EMPLOYED BY CN TO ASSIST IN THE OVERTHROW OF THE FRENCH MONARCHY AND THE DEFEAT OF ITS ARMY. A CN CONTROLLED REPUBLIC WITH A PUPPET GOVERNMENT IS ESTBLISHED. MAXIMILIEN ROBESPIERRE (CN) AND THE OTHER CN PUPPET LEADERS INSTITUTE 'LA TEREUR', TO WIT, TERRORISM AS OFFICIAL STATE POLICY, USHERING IN A CLIMATE OF FEAR AND PERSECUTION. MANY ARE GUILLOTINED INCLUDING THE KING. 25% OF THE FRENCH POPULATION ARE SAID TO LOSE THEIR LIVES AS A CONSEQUENCE OF THE CN'S POWER GRAB.

1799 CE: NAPOLEON BONAPARTE STAGES A COUP D'ETAT IN FRANCE. HE IS RUMOURED TO BE A CN AGENT, AND GOES ON TO ESTABLISH A EUROPE-WIDE EMPIRE. THE DIRECTION OF FRANCE FOLLOWING HIS DEFEAT IN 1815, ALLIED WITH THE CN CONTROLLED BRITISH EMPIRE, SUGGESTS THAT FRANCE'S SUBSEQUENT GOVERNMENTS ARE ALSO CN CONTROLLED, POSSIBLY WITH EXCEPTIONS. NAPOLEON'S WARS TO ESTABLISH HIS EUROPEAN EMPIRE, THEREFORE, MIGHT BE SEEN IN THE CONTEXT

OF A CN POWER CONSOLIDATION EXERCISE, USING WAR AS A COVER TO ARREST AND ELIMINATE OPPOSITION ACROSS EUROPE.

1833 CE: THE STATES OF VERMONT AND NEW YORK PASS LEGISLATION, RESTRICTING MASONIC ACTIVITIES. JOHN QUINCY ADAMS, FORMER PRESIDENT OF THE USA, STRONGLY CONDEMNS FREEMASONRY. HE HAS BECOME A MEMBER OF THE ANTI-MASONIC PARTY, ESTABLISHED IN 1828. MASONIC MEMBERSHIP PLUNGES. OF THE 450 LODGES KNOWN TO EXIST IN 1825, ONLY 50 KNOWN LODGES REMAIN IN 1834.

1843 CE: USA BASED LODGES OF THE ODDFELLOWS, A CN FRONT ORGANISATION MODELLED ON FREEMASONRY, CREATE THE INDEPENDENT ORDER OF ODD FELLOWS, TO REPLACE THE NOW UNPOPULAR FREEMASONRY AND ITS LODGES AS A PLACE FOR CN TO MEET, RAISE FUNDS AND RECRUIT. IN THE FOLLOWING YEARS, ODDFELLOWS LODGES WILL BE INSTITUTED ALL OVER THE USA, AS THE ORDER EXPERIENCES RAPID GROWTH. BY 1896, IT WILL HAVE BECOME THE LARGEST FRATERNAL ORGANISATION IN THE WORLD, WITH LODGES IN THE AMERICAS, AUSTRALASIA AND EUROPE. MANY OTHER CN FRONT ORGANISATIONS, SUCH AS THE ROYAL ANTEDILUVIAN ORDER OF BUFFALOES, ALSO BECOME POPULAR WITH THE GROWTH OF THE CN CONTROLLED BRITISH EMPIRE FRONT ORGANISATION.

1848 CE: THE CN EXECUTE A SERIES OF REVOLUTIONS BREAKS OUT ALL OVER EUROPE, WITH THE FIRST BEING IN FRANCE. OVER 50 COUNTRIES ARE AFFECTED, AND THE REVOLUTIONS GO ON UNTIL 1849. THE CN AIM TO REPLACE UNCOOPERATIVE AND ENEMY MONARCHIES WITH CN-FRIENDLY NATION-STATES. MANY OF THE REVOLUTIONS ARE QUICKLY SUPPRESSED, BUT SIGNIFICANT REFORMS ARE ENACTED ACROSS EUROPE. TENS OF THOUSANDS LOSE THEIR LIVES AND MANY MORE SEEK EXILE IN OTHER COUNTRIES, INCLUDING KARL MARX (CN), A JOURNALIST AND REVOLUTIONARY WHOSE NEWSPAPER IS CLOSED DOWN. HE LEAVES PRUSSIA, FIRST FOR FRANCE, THEN LONDON, CAPITAL OF THE CN CONTROLLED BRITISH EMPIRE, IN 1849, WHERE HE SHALL REMAIN UNTIL HIS DEATH IN 1883. SAFE IN FRIENDLY TERRITORY, HE SHALL WRITE 'CAPITAL', HIS THEORETICAL CRITIQUE OF POLITICAL ECONOMY, BETWEEN 1867 AND 1894, WHICH SHALL BECOME A SEMINAL REFERENCE DOCUMENT FOR SOCIALISTS AND COMMUNISTS. THE COMMUNIST LEAGUE HQ ALSO MOVES TO LONDON, AS DOES ANOTHER REVOLUTIONARY, KARL SCHAPPER (CN), UNTIL HIS DEATH IN 1870. SCHAPPER HAS INTERNATIONAL CONNECTIONS, SUCH AS GIUSEPPE MAZZINI (CN). MARX AND SCHAPPER, ARE MEMBERS OF THE LEAGUE OF THE JUST, A SUSPECTED CN FRONT ORGANISATION. SCHAPPER HELPS TO FOUND THE FIRST INTERNATIONAL IN LONDON IN 1864, AND COORDINATES INTERNATIONALLY WITH GROUPS AS

DIVERSE AS RADICALS, SOCIALISTS, TRADE UNIONISTS, COMMUNISTS AND BLANQUISTS, AND ALSO WITH THE VORMARZ AND RISORGIMENTO MOVEMENTS OF GERMANY AND ITALY. MARX IS FINANCIALLY SUSTAINED BY FRIEDRICH ENGELS (CN), WHOSE FAMILY ARE WEALTHY. THEY START TO WRITE FOR 6 NEWSPAPERS ACROSS THE WORLD. MARX WRITES FOR THE NEW-YORK DAILY TRIBUNE AS EUROPEAN CORRESPONDENT. THE NYDL SHALL CONTINUE UNTIL 1924, WHEN IT SHALL MERGE WITH THE NEW YORK HERALD TO BECOME THE NEW-YORK HERALD TRIBUNE, UNTIL 1966. THIS IS IMPORTANT TO NOTE, AS THE NYHT SHALL BE IDENTIFIED, ALONG WITH THE WASHINGTON POST AND THE NEW YORK TIMES, BY SENIOR AMERICA FIRST COMMITTEE OFFICERS, AS BRITISH SECURITY COORDINATION (A CN CONTROLLED BRITISH INTELLIGENCE SECTION) FRONT ORGANISATIONS, BEFORE THE SECOND WORLD WAR, DISSEMINATING PRO-BRITISH AND ANTI-GERMAN PROPAGANDA, TO ENSURE USA PARTICIPATION IN THE WAR ON THE BRITISH SIDE. THE CN ALSO START TO FOSTER ANTI-SEMITISM THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF CONSPIRACY THEORIES THAT BLAME THOSE OF THE JEWISH FAITH AS A CONVENIENT SCAPEGOAT FOR BOTH SOCIAL REVOLUTION AND INTERNATIONAL FINANCE, TO HIDE THEIR CONTROL OF BOTH. MARX'S NEWSPAPER 'NEUE RHEINISCHE ZEITUNG' WAS INVOLVED IN THE CREATION OF THIS MYTH. MARX IS A BRITISH INTELLIGENCE ASSET AND POSSIBLY A JESUIT. HIS ACTIVITIES ARE AIMED AT INFILTRATING AND HIJACK THE SOCIALIST AND COMMUNIST MOVEMENTS,

CREATING INTERNATIONAL REVOLUTIONARY STRUCTURES TO SPY ON THOSE GROUPS ACROSS THE WORLD, AND ORCHESTRATING SOCIAL UNREST AND REGIME CHANGE IN REGIMES UNFRIENDLY TO THE CN. THE NEW CN CONTROLLED MOVEMENT CREATED SHALL BECOME KNOWN AS MARXISM.

1861 CE: THE CN FOMENT A CIVIL WAR IN THE USA TO SUPPRESS OPPOSITION (OFTEN KILLED IN THE WAR), CEMENT CONTROL OVER THE USA BY IMPOVERISHING IT AS A RESULT OF THE WAR, SO THAT CN INVESTORS AND THE CN CONTROLLED BRITISH EMPIRE CAN PURCHASE CHEAP USA ASSETS AFTER THE WAR AND THEREBY CONTROL THE ECONOMY. THE WAR CONTINUES UNTIL 1865. JUDAH BENJAMIN (CN) AND ALBERT PIKE (CN), HAVING WORKED AND FOUGHT FOR THE CONFEDERATE SIDE, FLEE TO ENGLAND, AND BRITISH NORTH AMERICA (MODERN DAY CANADA), RESPECTIVELY. THEY BOTH WORK FOR CN CONTROLLED BRITISH EMPIRE INTELLIGENCE. PIKE, A 33RD DEGREE FREEMASON AND HEAD OF THE SOUTHERN JURISDICTION OF THE ANCIENT AND ACCEPTED SCOTTISH RITE, FOUNDS TWO RACIST AND TERRORIST ORGANISATIONS: THE KNIGHTS OF THE GOLDEN CIRCLE (A POSSIBLE REFERENCE TO THE SUN, AND THE CULT OF SOL INVICTUS OF ROME) IN BRITISH NORTH AMERICA, AND THE KNIGHTS OF THE KU KLUX KLAN IN THE USA. THE KKK HAS A FREEMASONIC STRUCTURE AND ITS CUSTOMS DRAW UPON PIKE'S FREEMASONRY. THEIR NAME IS AN ADAPTATION OF 'KYKLOS CLAN', WITH 'KYKLOS' BEING A GREEK WORK

MEANING 'CIRCLE'. IT MEANS, THUS, 'KNIGHTS OF THE CIRCLE CLAN'. HOWEVER, IN ORDER FOR THE NAME'S GEMATRIA TO ADD UP TO 33, A REFERENCE TO PIKE BEING A 33RD DEGREE FREEMASON, KCC HAD TO BECOME KKK. HENCE $K+K+K=11$ (TH LETTER)+11+11=33. THAT IS WHY KYKLOS WAS CHANGED TO KU KLUX. THE KKK IS ALSO SOMETIMES CALLED THE 'INVISIBLE EMPIRE', A REFERENCE TO THE INVISIBLE CN EMPIRE OF CN CONTROLLED STATES AND INFLUENCE.

1863 CE: ABRAHAM LINCOLN, PRESIDENT OF THE USA, ABOLISHES SLAVERY. SLAVERY IN THE USA HAD BEEN CHAMPIONED BY CN.

1865 CE: CN ASSASSINATE ABRAHAM LINCOLN, PRESIDENT OF THE UNITED STATES. HE HAD SPOKEN OUT AGAINST THE JESUIT ORDER (CN). ALBERT PIKE, IT IS SUSPECTED, WAS RUNNING CN ACTIVITIES IN NORTH AMERICA, AND PLANNED THE ASSASSINATION. HIS PEN NAME AS A JOURNALIST WAS 'CASCA', A REFERENCE TO PUBLIUS SERVILIUS CASCA LONGUS, ONE OF THE ASSASSINS OF JULIUS CAESAR IN 44 BCE. HE SHALL BE GIVEN AN OFFICIAL PARDON FOR HIS ROLE IN THE CIVIL WAR BY PRESIDENT ANDREW JOHNSON IN 1866. IT SHALL BE WRITTEN THAT HE MAKES PRESIDENT JOHNSON A 32ND FREEMASON IN THE OVAL OFFICE. THIS WOULD ORDINARILY BE AN IRREGULAR OCCURENCE, UNLESS PIKE CONFERS THE DEGREE USING HIS MASONIC

PREROGATIVE AS HEAD OF THE SOUTHERN JURISDICTION, WHICH IS POSSIBLE. IN THE ANCIENT AND ACCEPTED RITE OF ENGLAND AND WALES, TODAY, EQUIVALENT TO THE SCOTTISH RITE, THE DEGREES FROM 4TH TO 17TH ARE CONFERRED UPON A 3RD DEGREE MASTER MASON IN A SIMILAR WAY, ALL AT ONCE, IN A SIDE ROOM, BEFORE THE CANDIDATE ENTERS THE ROOM WHERE HE TAKES PART IN THE CEREMONY IN WHICH HE RECEIVES THE 18TH DEGREE. IN ANY EVENT, PIKE IS CLEARLY UNTOUCHABLE, AND ARGUABLY SENIOR TO PRESIDENT JOHNSON IN THE USA. A MEMORIAL TO HIM SHALL BE ERECTED IN WASHINGTON D.C. IN 1901.

1871 CE: ALBERT PIKE (CN) WRITES A LETTER TO GUISEPPE MAZZINI DETAILING THE CN PLAN TO TAKE OVER THE WORLD WITH THREE WORLD WARS AFTER DISCREDITING BOTH COMMUNISM AND PATRIOTISM.

1915 CE: THE RMS LUSITANIA IS SUNK BY THE ROYAL NAVY IN A FALSE FLAG ATTACK TO BLAME THE GERMAN NAVY AND ENCOURAGE USA PARTICIPATION IN THE WAR BY TURNING AMERICAN PUBLIC OPINION AGAINST GERMANY.

1917 CE: THE BALFOUR DECLARATION IS MADE AS A PUBLIC STATEMENT BY THE CN CONTROLLED BRITISH GOVERNMENT. IT CONSTITUTES A DECLARATION OF INTENT TO ESTABLISH A JEWISH STATE IN PALESTINE, IN LINE WITH THE CN PLAN OF PIKE'S LETTER, AND THE

PROGRESS OF WW1, INDICATING A FORESEEN CONTROL BY THE CN CONTROLLED BRITISH EMPIRE OF PALESTINE AFTER THE WAR.

1918 CE: THE GREAT WAR (WW1) CONCLUDES WITH A CN VICTORY, AS PER THE CN PLAN OF PIKE'S LETTER. THE CN CONTROLLED BRITISH EMPIRE STARTED THE WAR BY HIRING A SERBIAN NATIONALIST TO ASSASSINATE ARCHDUKE FRANZ FERDINAND OF AUSTRIA-HUNGARY. THE HABSBURG AND OSMAN DYNASTIES OF AUSTRIA-HUNGARY AND THE OTTOMAN EMPIRE ARE DEFEATED. AUSTRIA, HUNGARY AND GERMANY BECOME REPUBLICS UNDER CN CONTROL. TURKEY IS OCCUPIED BUT WILL FIGHT A WAR TO BECOME AN INDEPENDENT REPUBLIC IN 1923. THE REST OF OTTOMAN EMPIRE TERRITORY IS PARTITIONED AMONGST CN CONTROLLED STATES. THE CN IS NOW MORE OR LESS IN CONTROL OF THE ENTIRE WORLD, THROUGH ONE MEANS OR ANOTHER. THE HOUSES OF HABSBURG AND OSMAN HAD THOUGHT THEY COULD TRUST THE HOUSE OF HOHENZOLLERN, BUT THEY WERE DECEIVED. THE HOHENZOLLERN HAD BEEN CN AGENTS SINCE BEFORE THE CREATION OF PRUSSIA, WHEN THEIR ANCESTOR WAS IN THE TEUTONIC ORDER. THEY WERE ORDERED BY CN TO PARTICIPATE IN THE TRIPLE ALLIANCE TO ENCOURAGE THE HABSBURG AND OSMAN HOUSES, AND OTHER ALLIES, TO THINK THEY COULD WIN AGAINST THE (CN CONTROLLED) TRIPLE ENTENTE.

1917-1923 CE: VARIOUS CN CONTROLLED STATES INVADE THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE, LED BY THE BRITISH EMPIRE (OTHERWISE KNOWN AS RED EMPIRE DUE TO ITS ROMAN LINK AND THE COLOUR USED TO SHOW IT ON A MAP). TO HIDE THE CRIME OF KILLING TSAR NICHOLAS 2 FROM THE PUBLIC, THE CONQUEST OF RUSSIA IS DISGUISED AS A COMMUNIST REVOLUTION, AS PER THE PLAN OF ALBERT PIKE'S LETTER. THE NEW ARMY OF THE CN CONTROLLED SOVIET UNION THAT RESULTS, IS NAMED 'RED ARMY', A REFERENCE TO THE BRITISH ARMY (REDCOATS) AND THE ANCIENT ROMAN ARMY (WHO ALSO DRESSED IN RED). DECADES LATER, THE INTELLIGENCE AGENCY 'KGB' WILL BE CREATED (POSSIBLY AN ACRONYM IN ENGLISH AS WELL, FOR 'KINGDOM OF GREAT BRITAIN', A REFERENCE TO THE CN CONTROLLED KINGDOM THAT EXISTED BETWEEN 1707 AND 1800). THIS CN CONTROLLED AGENCY WILL COOPERATE WITH THE CN FOR AN UNKNOWN DURATION.

1945 CE: THE SECOND WORLD WAR, PLANNED BY CN AS PER PIKE'S LETTER, CONCLUDES WITH A CN VICTORY. IT IS A PHONY WAR FOUGHT BETWEEN CN CONTROLLED STATES AS A COVER FOR ELIMINATING AND NEUTRALISING OPPOSITION, PARTICULARLY COMMUNISTS, SOCIALISTS, LIBERALS, AND PERCEIVED OPPOSITION AND SCAPEGOATS SUCH AS SINTI, ROMA, YENISH, JEWISH AND AFRICAN ORIGIN PEOPLE. WINSTON CHURCHILL (CN) WORKS FOR MI5. FRANKLY DELANO ROOSEVELT (CN) WORKS FOR US NAVAL INTELLIGENCE. ADOLF HITLER (CN), BENITO

MUSSOLINI AND JOSEPH STALIN (CN) WORK FOR MI1C. THE WEIMAR REPUBLIC HAD BEEN UNDER BRITISH CONTROL AFTER WW1. THE WORD 'WEIMAR' MEANS 'HOLY LAKE' OR 'HOLY SEA' IN ENGLISH. IT IS POSSIBLE THAT THE REPUBLIC WAS NAMED AFTER WEIMAR IN GERMANY AS A CN REFERENCE TO THE HOLY SEE OR SAN MARINO, AN ORIGINALLY CN CONTROLLED STATE WHOSE NAME MEANS 'HOLY MARINER'. REFERENCES TO THIS THEME SEEM TO OFTEN OCCUR IN CN SYMBOLIC LANGUAGE BUT THE ORIGINAL REASON IS CURRENTLY UNKNOWN. ADOLF HITLER WAS A POINTMAN WORKING FOR KARL MAYR OF GERMAN MILITARY INTELLIGENCE AFTER THE WAR. HE WAS TASKED WITH INFILTRATING A POLITICAL PARTY, TAKING IT OVER, BUILDING ITS PUBLIC PROFILE AND SUPPORT, IN ORDER TO STAGE A COVERT/COVERED COUP D'ETAT (TRANSFERRING POLITICAL POWER TO THE MILITARY WITHOUT ARMED CONFLICT), IN THE SAME WAY THAT BENITO MUSSOLINI (CN) DID IN THE KINGDOM OF ITALY IN 1922, WITH THE HELP OF KING VICTOR EMMANUEL 3 (CN) OF ITALY. BOTH THE NAZI AND FASCIST PARTIES USED ROMAN SYMBOLS AND REFERENCES, SUCH AS THE TEUTONIC ORDER, FASCES AND EAGLE (SYMBOLS OF THE ROMAN EMPIRE MILITARY), ROMAN SALUTE, AND THE NAZI SLOGAN 'SEIG HEIL', MEANING 'HAIL VICTORY' IN ENGLISH AND 'AVE VICTORIA' IN LATIN, A REFERENCE TO THE ROMAN GODDESSE, VICTORY, AND 'AVE VICTORIA ROMANA', MEANING 'HAIL ROMAN VICTORY' IN LATIN. THE GERMAN MILITARY WERE SUPPOSED TO THINK THAT ADOLF HITLER HAD TAKEN BACK CONTROL OF GERMANY FROM THE

BRITISH WHEN HE HAD THE ENABLING ACT PASSED, AND ASSUMED ABSOLUTE POWER. HOWEVER, HE REMAINED IN CONTACT WITH MI6, WHO HAD RECRUITED HIM BEFORE WW1. IT SEEMS LIKELY HE WAS ABLE TO COMMUNICATE USING RECENTLY DEVELOPED TELECOMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGY SUCH AS A NEUROPHONE OR OTHER IMPLANT, ABLE TO RECEIVE RADIO MESSAGES FROM MI6. HE WAS ABLE TO RECEIVE INSTRUCTION BY OTHER MEANS, SUCH AS THROUGH THE CN IN ROME AND MOSCOW WHEN ON BUSINESS ABROAD BEFORE AND DURING WW2. HIS SECRET COLLABORATION WITH THE CN CONTROLLED BRITISH EMPIRE IS THE REASON FOR THE FOLLOWING: HE ALLOWED THE BRITISH EXPEDITIONARY FORCE TO ESCAPE FROM DUNKIRK. HE PRETENDED TO SEEK AN ALLIANCE WITH ENGLAND, WITH WHICH HE WAS AT WAR AND WHICH HE HAD IDENTIFIED IN 'MEIN KAMPF' (IN SO FAR AS HE WAS RESPONSIBLE FOR THAT PROBABLY GHOSTWRITTEN BOOK) AS BEING MERELY THE CENTRE OF 'THE BRITISH WORLD EMPIRE', WHICH MEANS OF COURSE THAT HE THOUGHT THE BRITISH EMPIRE, NOT PEOPLE OF THE JEWISH FAITH, WAS RULING THE WORLD, AND THUS RESPONSIBLE FOR ALL THE PROBLEMS AND PERCEIVED PROBLEMS HE IDENTIFIED IN GERMANY AND THE WHOLE WORLD AND RAILED AGAINST. HE NEVER IMPLEMENTED OPERATION SEALION, TO INVADE HIS ALLIES IN ENGLAND. ADMIRAL CANARIIS (ALSO MI6) GAVE AWAY U-BOAT POSITIONS TO THE ROYAL NAVY (THE ENIGMA MACHINE STORY WAS MADE UP AFTER WW2 TO EXPLAIN WHY THE ROYAL NAVY OFTEN SEEMED

TO KNOW THE POSITIONS OF GERMAN CRAFT). HE UNDERMINED HIS GENERALS INCLUDING ERWIN ROMMEL. HE FORCED THE GERMAN MILITARY TO FIGHT ON LONG AFTER VICTORY WAS IMPOSSIBLE: THE ALLIES FACED ADOLESCENTS IN GERMAN UNIFORM IN BERLIN FOR WANT OF SUFFICIENT NUMBERS OF ADULT GERMAN SOLDIERS LEFT TO FIGHT, AND HITLER ORDERED FIELD MARSHAL PAULUS TO FIGHT UNTIL THE LAST MAN AT STALINGRAD, MEANING HIS INTENTION WAS CLEARLY TO SEE KILLED, AN ENTIRE GENERATION OF YOUNG GERMAN, SOVIET UNION, AND OTHER ALLIED FORCES', MEN.

1945-PRESENT: I HAVE THEORIES AND MUCH INFORMATION, MUCH OF WHICH ARE HIGHLY SENSITIVE FROM A POLITICAL POINT OF VIEW, AND RELATE TO PERSONS STILL LIVING. I AM AVAILABLE FOR FURTHER COMMENT.

CAUSA NOSTRA TERROR GROUP STRUCTURE (SUSPECTED)

THE BLACK NOBILITY ARE THE DESCENDANTS OF ROMAN EMPIRE ERA ARISTOCRATIC FAMILIES, ATTEMPTING TO RE-ESTABLISH A WORLD-WIDE ROMAN EMPIRE, 'IMPERIUM ROMANUM' OR 'I.R.' FOR SHORT ('ROMAN EMPIRE' IN LATIN), HAVING MOSTLY SUCCEEDED IN SECRET, BUT FURTHER SEEKING TO MAKE THEIR EMPIRE PUBLIC.

BY THEIR ROMAN LAW, THE BREAK UP OF THE ROMAN EMPIRE, THE WESTERN PART IN 476 CE, THEN THE EASTERN PART (BYZANTINE EMPIRE) IN 1453 CE, WAS ILLEGAL. THUS, THEY WOULD BE LEGALLY ENTITLED BY THEIR SHADOW/CRYPTO/SECRET LEGAL SYSTEM, TO DO EVERYTHING THEY COULD DO, TO ENSURE THE RE-ESTABLISHMENT OF ROMAN RULE, AND EXPAND THEIR EMPIRE WORLD-WIDE. THEY DO NOT RECOGNISE ANY OTHER LEGAL SYSTEM, OTHER THAN THEIR OWN, WHICH THEY THINK SUPERSEDES ALL OTHERS. THEY SEE THEIR MISSION AS A MILITARY CAMPAIGN, AND USE MILITARY STRATEGIES AND TACTICS SUCH AS CAMOUFLAGE AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WARFARE TO ACHIEVE FINAL, TOTAL VICTORY. THUS, THEY ARE THE ROMAN MILITARY TODAY, JUST AS THEY WERE BEFORE 476 CE, THOUGH THEY DISGUISE THEMSELVES BEHIND MANY MASKS TO ACHIEVE THEIR MILITARY OBJECTIVE.

THE CAUSA NOSTRA TERROR GROUP ENGAGES IN MANY AREAS OF ACTIVITY, WITH A VIEW TO TAKING OVER EVERY UN MEMBER STATE GOVERNMENT COMPLETELY. AFTER SUCCESSFULLY TAKING OVER A TARGET GOVERNMENT, IT RAPIDLY INCORPORATES THAT GOVERNMENT INTO ITS POLITICAL DIVISION, RECRUITING ALL THOSE IT CAN AND TARGETING ALL OPPOSITION. IT CAN THEN USE ITS FINANCES, RESOURCES, INFLUENCE, MILITARY AND FOREIGN INTELLIGENCE NETWORK FOR FURTHER OPERATIONS. IT OPERATES THROUGH MANY DIFFERENT TYPES OF

FRONT ORGANISATION TO ACHIEVE ITS OBJECTIVES. THE ROMAN ARISTOCRATIC (BLACK NOBILITY) FAMILIES CONTROL THE CRIMINAL AND POLITICAL DIVISION, THROUGH WHICH THEY CONTROL ALL THE OTHERS. THEY ARE OFTEN BASED IN ITALY, WHERE ITALIAN CRIMINAL ORGANISATIONS (MAFIA SUCH AS CAMORRA) ALSO OPERATE. THE CAUSA NOSTRA EMPLOYS A CELLULAR STRUCTURE IN ITS ORGANISATION, MUCH AS THE BAVARIAN ILLUMINATI OF THE CRYPTO-JESUIT AND CAUSA NOSTRA AGENT ADAM WEISHAUP DID. THIS WILL BE FAMILIAR TO LAW ENFORCEMENT OFFICERS AS THE SAME ONE TERRORIST ORGANISATIONS OFTEN USE, ATTEMPTING TO ENSURE THAT IN THE EVENT OF THE ARREST OF THE MEMBERS OF, AND THE CLOSING DOWN OF, ONE CELL, THE REST OF THE ORGANISATION SURVIVES INTACT TO CARRY ON ITS OPERATIONS. E.G. RATHER THAN HAVE ONE ORGANISATION OF 100000 PEOPLE, THEY PREFER 10 SIMILAR, PERHAPS RELATED, BUT DISTINCT, ORGANISATIONAL CELLS OF 10000 PEOPLE EACH. IF ONE CELL IS COMPROMISED OR DISCREDITED, THE OTHER 90000 PEOPLE IN THE ORGANISATION MIGHT REMAIN UNAFFECTED AND ABLE TO REMAIN ACTIVE.

LEVEL 1: BLACK NOBILITY FAMILIES.

CRIMINAL DIVISION

CRIMINAL ORGANISATIONAL CELLS SPECIALISE IN DIFFERENT GEOGRAPHIC AREAS AND/OR CRIMINAL ACTIVITIES, IN ORDER TO RAISE OFF-THE-BOOKS FUNDS FOR FURTHER OPERATIONS.

LEVEL 2: MAFIA AND OTHER CRIMINAL ORGANISATION CHIEFS (NDRANGHETA, MAFIA CENTRALE, CAMORRA, CALI CARTEL ETC).

LEVEL 3: PROFESSIONAL CRIMINAL ORGANISATION MEMBERS (MADE MEN ETC).

LEVEL 4: CRIMINAL ORGANISATION ASSOCIATES.

POLITICAL DIVISION

LEVEL 2: CURIA.

LEVEL 3: 'THE ENTITY' WITHIN ORDERS/CELLS (DOMINICANS, JESUITS ETC).

LEVEL 4: CN HEADS OF STATE (CHARLES WINDSOR ETC).

LEVEL 5: CN DOMESTIC INTELLIGENCE AGENCIES' CHIEFS (MI5 ETC).

LEVEL 6: CN GOVERNMENT MINISTERS.

LEVEL 7: CN CHIEFS OF POLICE (EG UK CROWN SERVANTS), MILITARY (EG USA AREA AND WINDSOR LOYAL ROYAL MILITARY), AND FOREIGN INTELLIGENCE AGENCIES (E.G. MI6: SIS, CSIS, ASIS, NWSIS, ISIS [MOSSAD], SVR AND CIA [RUSSIAN FEDERATION AND USA CORPORATE INTELIGENCE WORKING FOR THE UK CROWN]).

LEVEL 8: CN POLICE INTELLIGENCE AND MILITARY INTELLIGENCE CHIEFS.

FINANCIAL DIVISION

REGARDLESS OF ORIGIN, FUNDS ARE TRANSFERRED TO CITY OF LONDON (FORMERLY 'LONDINIUM'), A VATICAN CITY (PREVIOUSLY ROMAN EMPIRE, THEN PAPAL STATES) POSSESSION, INDEPENDENT AND OUTSIDE UK AND UN JURISDICTION, WITH THE LORD MAYOR AS HEAD OF STATE. CLEAN FUNDS THEN LEAVE THE CITY EN ROUTE FOR THE UN ECONOMY.

ALSO, FUNDS CAN LEAVE VATICAN CITY FOR OFFSHORE JURISDICTIONS SET UP TO ENSURE BANKING SECRECY, SUCH AS BRITISH VIRGIN ISLANDS. ACCOUNT BALANCES CAN BE USED TO SET

UP COMPANIES IN THOSE JURISDICTIONS, WHICH CAN THEN INVEST IN THE WIDER UN ECONOMY. ONE METHOD IS TO SET UP A FILIAL COMPANY IN A STATE, SUCH AS THE UK, WHICH THEN MAKES A PROFIT. HOWEVER, THE PARENT COMPANY IN THE OFFSHORE JURISDICTION CHARGES MANAGEMENT AND OTHER FEES TO THE FILIAL COMPANY, REDUCING ITS PROFITS. THUS, THE FILIAL COMPANY MAKES AS SMALL A PROFIT AS POSSIBLE, MINIMISING TAX PAYMENTS. THE PARENT COMPANY MAKES A PROFIT, BUT IN AN OFFSHORE JURISDICTION WHERE IS LITTLE TO NO TAX TO PAY.

LEVEL 3: VATICAN BANK CHIEF (INSTITUTE FOR THE WORKS OF RELIGION) CAN CREATE INFINITE MONEY IN ITS BANK ACCOUNTS, OUTSIDE UN/INTERPOL JURISDICTION, WITH NO LEGAL OVERSIGHT.

LEVEL 4: LORD MAYOR OF LONDON AND OFFSHORE JURISDICTION CHIEFS.

LEVEL 5: TRUSTED BANK, FINANCIAL AND CORPORATE MANAGERS.

BLACK PROPAGANDA AND SUBVERSION DIVISION

SEEKS TO SPREAD RUMOURS AND UNDERMINE TARGET STATE'S CULTURAL VALUES, MORALITY AND LAW-ABIDING BEHAVIOUR, SOCIAL COHESION AND ANYTHING ELSE THEY DEEM NECESSARY IN THE

TARGET STATE, TO UNDERMINE, DIVIDE AND OPPRESS THE POPULATION. THE CN FOLLOWS THE ANCIENT ROMAN PRINCIPLE 'DIVIDE ET IMPERA' (DIVIDE AND RULE/CONTROL). PSYOPS (PSYCHOLOGICAL OPERATIONS) CAN BE DIRECTED AT THE OCCUPIED POPULATION TO SPREAD FEAR AND HATRED E.G. 'ACID RAIN', THE 'COLD WAR' (BOTH USA AND SOVIET UNION WERE WINDSOR CONTROLLED CRYPTO-COLONIES WHOSE MI6 CONTROLLED LEADERS PRETENDED TO OPPOSE EACH OTHER TO CONTROL THEIR RESPECTIVE POPULATIONS THROUGH THE DREAD OF A PROSPECTIVE NUCLEAR WAR).

LEVELS 5 AND 7: CN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN INTELLIGENCE AGENCIES' CHIEFS.

LEVELS 6 AND 8: SUBVERSIVE ORGANISATION CHIEFS (E.G. PEDOPHILE INFORMATION EXCHANGE, ORGANISATIONS GLORIFYING CRIMINAL MINDSETS AND BEHAVIOURS); CN MEDIA CHIEFS E.G. NEWSPAPER OWNERS, EDITORS, AND CINEMA CORPORATION OWNERS, PRODUCERS AND DIRECTORS.

LEVELS 6 AND 8: SUBVERSIVE ORGANISATION MEMBERS; CN JOURNALISTS, SCRIPT WRITERS AND ACTORS.

EXTREMISM PROMOTION DIVISION

USEFUL FOR PLANNING FUTURE STATE-OF-PLAY AND BUILDING TOWARDS IT, EMPLOYING HEGELIAN DIALECTIC STRATEGY (PROBLEM/THESIS - REACTION/ANTITHESIS - SOLUTION/SYNTHESIS). DOMESTIC INTELLIGENCE AGENCIES IN ROMAN CONTROLLED AREAS CAN CREATE POLITICAL AND OTHER GROUPS THAT INDOCTRINATE, RECRUIT AND TRAIN DISCONTENTED CITIZENS IN EXTREMIST IDEOLOGIES, TO ACCOMPLISH SET OBJECTIVES.

FOR INSTANCE, A CN CONTROLLED 'COMMUNIST' PARTY MIGHT BE USED TO ATTACK A BUILDING, PROVIDING A CATALYST FOR A PLANNED CHANGE, BY GENERATING A REACTION FROM CN CONTROLLED 'NATIONALISTS', WHO THEN STAGE A DEMONSTRATION, LEADING THE 'COMMUNISTS' TO ATTACK THE DEMONSTRATION, AND AN ENSUING RIOT THAT CAN BE USED TO THE CN'S ADVANTAGE AS A JUSTIFICATION FOR BRINGING IN LEGISLATION TO RESTRICT THE FREEDOM TO DEMONSTRATE.

LEVELS 5: CN DOMESTIC INTELLIGENCE AGENCIES' CHIEFS.

LEVELS 6: EXTREMIST ORGANISATION CHIEFS (E.G. REVOLUTIONARY, NEO-NAZI AND OTHER POLITICAL GROUPS).

LEVEL 7: LOCAL EXTREMIST ORGANISATION (CELL) HEADS.

LEVEL 8: EXTREMIST ORGANISATION MEMBERS.

TERRORIST DIVISION

USEFUL FOR PLANNING FUTURE STATE-OF-PLAY AND BUILDING TOWARDS IT, EMPLOYING HEGELIAN DIALECTIC STRATEGY (PROBLEM/THESIS - REACTION/ANTITHESIS - SOLUTION/SYNTHESIS). DOMESTIC INTELLIGENCE AGENCIES IN CN CONTROLLED AREAS CAN CREATE TERRORIST ORGANISATIONS THAT INDOCTRINATE, RECRUIT AND TRAIN DISCONTENTED CITIZENS IN EXTREMIST IDEOLOGIES, TO CARRY OUT TERROR ATTACKS IN ORDER TO ACCOMPLISH SET OBJECTIVES E.G. FALSE FLAG ATTACKS.

LEVEL 5: CN DOMESTIC INTELLIGENCE AGENCIES' CHIEFS.

LEVEL 6: TERRORIST ORGANISATION HEADS (E.G. AL QAIDA, IS, COMBAT 18, IRA ETC).

LEVEL 7: TERRORIST CELL CHIEFS.

LEVEL 8: TERRORIST ORGANISATION MEMBERS.

INFLUENCE AND RECRUITMENT DIVISION

LEVEL 3: CN JESUITS, PRO DEO ETC

LEVEL 4: CN HEADS OF CHARITIES, CLUBS, RELIGIOUS AND OTHER ORGANISATIONS, SUCH AS GRAND MASTERS OF FREEMASONIC GRAND LODGES AND GRAND ORIENTS, HEADS OF ODDFELLOWS, BLACK INSTITUTION, CULTS AND OTHERS.

LEVEL 5: RECRUITMENT POOL.

BUSINESS DIVISION

VARIOUS LEVELS, RECRUIT BUSINESSMEN TO SET UP AND RUN BUSINESSES IN THEIR NAME, OR THE BUSINESSMAN'S NAME, TO RAISE FUNDS WHILE GIVING THE ILLUSION OF LESS ORGANISATIONAL WEALTH THAN IS TRUE IN REALITY.

POPULAR LIVING STANDARDS AND INFORMATION SUPPRESSION DIVISION

LEVELS 1, 2, 3, 4 AND 5 SUPPRESS ALL INFORMATION ABOUT THE CN CONSPIRACY, INCLUDING HISTORICAL INFORMATION, AND NEW TECHNOLOGIES, INVENTIONS AND PATENTS THAT COULD LEAD TO INCREASED LIVING STANDARDS AMONGST THE PEOPLE, PARTICULARLY THE POOR. WHEN PEOPLE BECOME EDUCATED AND WEALTHY, SOCIAL MOBILITY CAN OCCUR OUTSIDE THE CONTROL OF CN. THAT CONSTITUTES A THREAT TO CN CONTROL OF SOCIETY AS INDEPENDENT PEOPLE ARE NO LONGER UNDER CN CONTROL AND ARE THUS THEN FREE TO OPPOSE THEM AND THEIR POLICIES.

SURVEILLANCE DIVISION

LEVELS 1, 2, 3, 4 AND 5 RECRUIT PRIVATE INTELLIGENCE AGENCIES (E.G. 'BLACK CUBE', 'AEGIS' ETC) TO PERFORM OFF-THE-BOOKS SURVEILLANCE OF CERTAIN KEY TARGETS, ESPECIALLY WHEN THAT SURVEILLANCE CANNOT BE JUSTIFIED BY A STATE GOVERNMENT IF THEY ARE DISCOVERED AND PROSECUTED. THUS, USE OF A PRIVATE COMPANY CREATES A FIREWALL BETWEEN THE AGENCY AND THE STATE SO THE STATE HAS 'PLAUSIBLE DENIABILITY'.

ENFORCEMENT DIVISION

LEVELS 1, 2, 3 AND 4 RECRUIT PRIVATE MILITARY (E.G. BLACKWATER) FOR CLANDESTINE ENFORCEMENT CAMPAIGNS AND OPERATIONS, AGAINST TARGET STATES, ORGANISATIONS OR INDIVIDUALS. EX-MILITARY PERSONNEL, OFTEN EX-SPECIAL FORCES, CAN BE RECRUITED THROUGH THE CORPS OF COMMISSIONAIRES AND OTHER ORGANISATIONS, FOR PRIVATE ORGANISATIONS E.G. 'CORPS SECURITY'.

Further reading:

UK COMPANIES - ILLEGAL UNDER INTERNATIONAL LAW, PLEASE SEE LINKS:

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE022348>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE027515>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE029215>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE015146>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE028105>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE026833>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE024899>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE027503>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/03259922>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE011807>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE022348>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE022540>

Undue foreign influence in EU affairs:

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE011807>

Of possible interest vis-à-vis drug trade:

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE022348>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE022540>

Undue influence in Laos affairs:

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/officers/BRrUIUZRH2LLYc3j1N0MR0-Byf0/appointments>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/09112837>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/09774296>

Undue influence in Yemeni affairs:

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/10929575>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/10801289>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/03259922>

Undue influence in Myanmar affairs:

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE011777>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE026520>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE029215>

Undue influence in Spanish affairs:

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/officers/7DRiSCZv3KfkjCHEo6Yz5rVvv9w/appointments>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/13249188>

<https://www.catalannews.com/politics/item/cup-the-party-seeking-independence-through-subversion>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE013388>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE022351>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE016890/filing-history>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE028502/persons-with-significant-control>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE027811>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/RC000039>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/BR001417/filing-history>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/FC002851>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/03226975/filing-history?page=8>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/RC000042>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/RC000043>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE023610>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/company/OE019176/filing-history>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/search?q=reserve+bank>

<https://find-and-update.company-information.service.gov.uk/search?q=bank+of>

<https://reense.com/general62/britt.htm>

<https://aim4truth.org/2018/04/17/exposed-all-the-queens-agents-and-corporations-that-control-the-world/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/how-venetian-system-transplanted-englandwebster-g-tarpley-forgione>

